

PULMONARY HYPERTENSION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract. *Pulmonary hypertension associated with chronic kidney disease (CKD) is an important yet under-recognized condition and can lead to life-threatening complications. The pathogenesis of pulmonary hypertension is peculiar in CKD, and understanding it is important to recognize such patients at the earliest and commence appropriate treatment. Many studies have discovered the prevalence of pulmonary hypertension to be up to 80% in CKD and have been associated with increased mortality. WHO has classified pulmonary hypertension in renal failure to be in group 5, a group defined by unclear multifactorial etiologies? The pharmacological management of pulmonary hypertension in this unique population is not very different from other etiologies. However, one should understand that pulmonary hypertension as such, could be multifactorial, and other secondary causes of pulmonary hypertension should also be recognized and treated accordingly. In this article, we will discuss the concept of pulmonary hypertension in CKD in detail and the options of treatment.*

Keywords: *chronic kidney disease, end-stage renal disease, pulmonary hypertension, cardiovascular diseases.*

Introduction. CKD can lead to multiple systemic life-threatening complications, including cardiovascular diseases. Pulmonary arterial hypertension, defined as elevated blood pressure in the pulmonary artery, can be a definite risk factor for both morbidities as well as mortality in the patients with CKD. Though various theories have been postulated as the cause of pulmonary hypertension, a commonly accepted hypothesis is that it is because of increased cardiac output in these patients from the arteriovenous fistulas created for hemodialysis access. Calcifications of the pulmonary artery are found in patients who are treated with hemodialysis [1].

Pulmonary hypertension (PH) is defined as mean pulmonary artery pressure (mPAP) of at least 25 mm Hg at rest. The consensus Dana Point classification categorizes PH into 5 distinct groups based on the etiology or pathophysiology (table 1) [2]. A distinction is made between pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) (group 1) and other causes of raised pulmonary arterial pressure such as heart failure. PAH is a progressive condition characterized by endothelial dysfunction and re-modelling of pulmonary vascular medial and intimal layers resulting in constrictive and occlusive vascular lesions respectively. To fulfil the diagnostic criteria for PAH, the pulmonary capillary wedge pressure (PCWP) should be <15 mm Hg with pulmonary vascular resistance >3 WU.

Recent observational studies have reported a high prevalence of PH in end-stage renal disease (ESRD), particularly among hemodialysis (HD) patients [3–5] and an association with adverse outcomes.

The world health organization (WHO) classified pulmonary hypertension into five groups based on the etiology, which was further revised in 2003 and 2008. Group 1 included (Idiopathic pulmonary arterial hypertension (IPAH), drug or toxin-induced pulmonary hypertension, inheritable pulmonary hypertension explained by specific gene mutations, collagen vascular

diseases, HIV induced pulmonary hypertension, parasitic Infections like Schistosomiasis, and Chronic hemolytic anemia. Pulmonary hypertension induced by left heart failure including valvular disease, pulmonary venoocclusive disease, and extrinsic compression of pulmonary veins are included in group 2 pulmonary hypertension. Pulmonary hypertension occurring as a result of chronic lung diseases including obstructive sleep apnea, belong to group 3 pulmonary hypertension [6]. Group 4 pulmonary hypertension is chronic thrombo- embolic pulmonary hypertension (CTEPH). Pulmonary hypertension with other less clear or multifactorial etiology are considered in group 5. Multiple etiologies including ESRD, are designated under this category. Our focus will be on pulmonary hypertension secondary to end-stage renal disease.

Prevalence estimates of PH in patients with CKD are based primarily on echocardiographic parameters with little validation using the recommended gold standard right heart catheterization (RHC). Due to the lack of prospective case-controlled studies, the timing of PH onset and its cumulative incidence at progressive stages of CKD are unknown.

Data on PH prevalence among CKD stage 5 patients prior to the initiation of renal replacement therapy (RRT) are scarce. One retrospective cohort study by Yigla et al. [7] reported a prevalence of 13.7% among 127 pre-dialysis patients, but did not provide data regarding excretory function at the time of echocardiography. Another study reported a much higher prevalence of PH in patients with advanced CKD not on RRT (39%), rising to 56% in those established on dialysis [8]. A similar prevalence in conservatively managed ESRD patients (32%) was reported by Abdelwhab and Elshinnawy [9]. In patients established on RRT, PH has been reported to be more prevalent affecting 30–58% of patients receiving HD [3, 5, 11, 12] with the largest and most recent study reporting a prevalence of 38% [10]. In patients receiving peritoneal dialysis (PD) the reported prevalence varies between 12.5 and 42% [13]. Table 1 summarizes these studies.

Table 1 Summary of studies

Reference (first author)	Design	Population	Number	Definition of PH	Prevalence rate	Incidence rate
Amin	cross-sectional	HD	51	sPAP >35 mm Hg	29.4%	N/A
2003 [6]						
Yigla	cross-sectional	HD	58	sPAP >35 mm Hg	39.7%	N/A
2003 [5]						
Yigla	cross-sectional	HD	49	sPAP >35 mm Hg	57%	N/A
2004 [13]						
Nakhoul	cross-sectional	HD	42	sPAP >35 mm Hg	48%	N/A
2005 [14]						
Havlucu	prospective	HD and	HD: 25	sPAP >35 mm Hg	HD: 56%	not reported
2007 [8]		pre-dialysis	pre-dialysis: 23		conservative: 39%	

Kumbar	retrospective	PD	36	sPAP >35 mm Hg	42%	N/A
2007 [13]						
Yigla	prospective	pre-dialysis prior to creation of AVF	12	sPAP >35 mm Hg	0%	41.7% after formation of AVF
2008 [15]						
Unal	cross-sectional	PD	135	sPAP >35 mm Hg	12.5%	N/A
2009 [4]						
Unal	prospective	HD	20	sPAP >35 mm Hg	30%	20% over a mean
2010 [11]						23.5 months
Yigla	retrospective	HD	127	sPAP >45 mm Hg	before initiation of	15.7% after
2009 [7]					HD: 13.4% after	initiation of HD
					initiation of HD: 29%	(time scale variable)
Ramasubbu	longitudinal	HD	90	tricuspid jet >2.5 m/s	47%	N/A
2010 [11]	(mortality/morbidity study)					
Fabbian	cross-sectional	HD and PD	HD: 29	sPAP >35 mm Hg	overall: 39%	N/A
2011 [3]			PD: 27		PD: 18.5%	
					HD: 58.6%	
Agarwal	longitudinal	HD	288	sPAP >35 mm Hg	38%	N/A
2012 [10]	mortality					
Pabst	cross-sectional	pre-dialysis	62	RHC mPAP >25 mm Hg	pre-dialysis:	N/A
2012 [16]		and HD with unexplained breathlessness		pre-capillary:	pre-capillary: 6%	
				PCWP <15 mm Hg	post-capillary: 71%	
				post-capillary:	HD:	
				PCWP >15 mm Hg	pre-capillary: 13%	
					post-capillary: 65%	

No studies have reported a gender-specific risk for PH in renal disease. Similarly, studies that specifically looked at the prevalence of ischaemic heart disease [7, 12, 13, 17] or traditional cardiac risk factors such as cholesterol or smoking [3, 4, 7, 13] reported no increased preponderance of these factors in patients with PH.

Several mechanisms for PH in advanced CKD have been proposed and are discussed below (fig. 1). Both systolic and diastolic cardiac dysfunctions are common in CKD. There are numerous causes for heart failure in CKD, including hypertension, salt and water overload, pleiotropic effects of uraemic toxins and myocardial ischaemia. Most studies found correlations between the presence of PH and echocardiographic features of primary cardiac dysfunction. There is no consensus, however, regarding the echocardiographic findings that best predict PH in patients with advanced CKD or ESRD. In one study of 127 patients, of whom 37 had PH defined as an echocardiographically estimated systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP) >45 mm Hg, there was a significantly higher prevalence of valvular disease (54% compared to 13% in those without PH), mostly mild mitral regurgitation [7]. There was a significantly higher prevalence of left ventricular (LV) dilatation and systolic dysfunction, although there was no difference in the prevalence of LV diastolic dysfunction between patients with and without PH.

A smaller study including 56 patients on HD and PD reported that 100% of those with PH had mitral valve incompetence [3], compared to 79% of those without PH. Mitral valve incompetence in HD patients is usually functional and merely reflects the fluid status of the patient, with changes in severity according to timing of echocardiography in relation to dialysis and ultrafiltration [18]. The only other significant echocardiographic difference was ejection fraction which was significantly lower in the PH group (54 vs. 60%). In the same study, a lower diastolic blood pressure was noted in patients with PH despite a similar systolic blood pressure. This may suggest a role for arterial stiffness in the pathogenesis of the condition, as low diastolic systemic blood pressure, especially in the context of wide pulse pressure in the elderly, has been associated with increased arterial stiffness and mortality [19].

In a study of patients receiving PD, LV mass index, alongside low serum albumin and fluid overload, was a predictor of sPAP in a multivariate model [4]. Conversely, another study of patients receiving PD found no difference in the prevalence of LV hypertrophy, though LV dilatation was more prevalent in patients with PH [13].

Agarwal's study [12] also showed no difference in LV mass index between patients with PH and those without. In fact, paradoxically, patients with PH had a higher cardiac index and mid-wall fractional shortening implying a better systolic function. In a multivariate model, left atrial diameter was the strongest predictor of PH. As left atrial diameter is a strong predictor of diastolic dysfunction, the findings suggest that in this group of patients, diastolic dysfunction may be a more relevant mechanism for PH.

The diastolic dysfunction in advanced CKD patients is likely to be exacerbated by chronic fluid overload. To date, most studies of PH in CKD have failed to adequately adjust for fluid status. There are several reasons for this including the lack of a satisfactory definition of euvolaemia, the absence of a gold standard method for assessing fluid status in the CKD population and the variation between patients in the ratio of total body water to intravascular volume.

The study of Unal et al. [4] tried to address the relationship between fluid overload and PH. Fluid overload was determined using bioimpedance studies and was expressed as extracellular to intracellular water ratio (ECW: ICW). There was a significantly higher prevalence of PH in fluid

overloaded compared to normovolaemic patients (27 vs. 3.6%) with a direct correlation between ECW:ICW ratio and PAP. However, whether optimizing fluid status reduced PAP was not determined.

Pabst et al. [16] showed a significant reduction in PAP, and hence prevalence of PH, when RHC and echocardiographic measurements were repeated post-dialysis. Such acute changes in PAP are most likely to be due to fluid ultrafiltration. The resultant drops in PCWP changed the diagnosis from post-capillary PH to pre-capillary PH (PAH) in 4 out of 24 patients. However, these findings should not be over-interpreted. Firstly, for the majority of the dialysis population, 'euvolaemia' achieved immediately post-dialysis is only short-lived as fluid starts to accumulate. Secondly, PCWP may be a poor indicator of LV end-diastolic pressure (LVEDP), where in one study about half of the patients diagnosed with PAH based on PCWP <15 mm Hg had elevated LVEDP on left heart catheterisation [20].

Of course, fluid overload may cause a direct lung injury from chronic pulmonary congestion adding yet a further pathophysiological mechanism to PH in these patients.

Fig. 1. Potential mechanisms contributing to PH in CKD. Hypertension, fluid overload, AVF and myocardial ischaemia result in heart failure and group 2 PH, whilst uraemic vasculopathy (vascular calcification and endothelial dysfunction) may result in increased pulmonary vascular resistance and PAH-type pathology. Other contributing factors include thromboembolism from dialysis access, chronic pulmonary oedema and obstructive sleep apnoea

The autopsy on patients who had ESRD showed that up to 40–80% of them had metastatic calcifications, though the chest radiology rarely reveals these calcifications [20]. The chronically elevated parathyroid hormone makes the hallmark of ESRD and results in the mobilization of calcium into cells. Akmal et al. hypothesized that one of the main reasons for pulmonary artery calcifications is secondary hyperparathyroidism [21]. They also postulated that secondary pulmonary hypertension with right ventricular functional abnormalities. This was further confirmed as surgical removal of canine parathyroid glands with chronic renal failure reduced

pulmonary artery calcifications. Apart from pulmonary artery calcifications, hormonal, and metabolic changes in ESRD results in vasoconstriction leading to pulmonary hypertension [23]. Levels of vasoactive substances including tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), Interleukin 1b (IL-1B), IL-6, acute phase proteins etc., were high in this subset of patients pointing towards a chronic inflammatory etiology [24].

Such patients also had higher levels of nitric oxide that was fractionally excreted in the airways. Arterio-venous (AV) fistula that is surgically made in the patients who are on dialysis is the cause of pulmonary hypertension in a considerable population, though most of the patients who have pulmonary hypertension have co-existing heart conditions contributing to the elevated pulmonary arterial pressure. Pulmonary hypertension can develop quickly after fistula formation sometimes even before the commencement of hemodialysis through the fistula [25]. The significant increase in cardiac output reduced systemic vascular resistance and hence increased venous return often caused by the AV fistula needs to be accommodated by the pulmonary vessels. Endothelial dysfunction noted in these vessels due to ESRD causes decreased ability to adapt to the higher cardiac output and results in increased PA pressure [26].

This is also further supported by the reduced levels of nitric oxide in patients with pulmonary hypertension in ESRD and the levels improve with hemodialysis. Together with reduced NO, there is also increased asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) which is an inhibitor of endothelin synthase.

The possible causes of pulmonary hypertension and the associated confounding factors in patients with ESRD with and without AV fistula are depicted in the figure (Fig. 2). Volume overload in ESRD is a direct cause of increased blood pressure in the pulmonary artery from increased after-load, especially if there is co-existing LV disorder. Interestingly pulmonary hypertension can reverse if the AV fistula is closed or after renal transplant. The presence of pulmonary hypertension in dialysis patients does increase the mortality rate and kidney transplants should be considered in ESRD patients with known prior pulmonary hypertension. The same applies if a patient develops pulmonary hypertension after initiation of renal replacement therapy with hemodialysis. Also, there is no survival advantage in peritoneal dialysis over hemodialysis though it does not involve the need for creating an AV fistula [27]. It proves that apart from AV fistula, there are other parameters involved in the pathogenesis of pulmonary hypertension in ESRD. Chronic anemia in patients with ESRD is an essential cause of hypoxia that in turn, paves the way to the development of pulmonary hypertension.

Fig. 2 Possible mechanism of development of pulmonary hypertension which are unique to

CKD/ESRD patients

A substantial body of evidence associates uraemia with chronic inflammation. Increases in pro-inflammatory monocytes, mast-cell proliferation, T-lymphocyte dysfunction, and decreased T-regulatory cells which result in an immune dysfunction are reported [28]. An increase in circulating inflammatory mediators also causes an increase in oxidative stress resulting in endothelial dysfunction. Patients with CKD have elevated levels of vasoconstrictors such as endothelin-1 and angiotensin II and reduced levels of endogenously produced vasodilators such as nitric oxide (NO) [29]. This imbalance of vasoactive peptides can directly affect pulmonary vascular tone and might mediate an increase in pulmonary vascular resistance causing PAH.

One study showed reduced NO levels and attenuated release of NO in response to HD in patients with PH compared to patients receiving HD without PH [30]. However, another study of 135 patients treated with PD showed no correlation between PH and asymmetric dimethylarginine, a uraemic toxin and inhibitor of NO synthase [4].

The direct effects of uraemic toxins are difficult to assess. Similarly, the effect of uraemic toxin clearance by dialysis on mortality is not fully understood. For example, the landmark HEMO study showed no overall survival benefit in patients receiving higher dose dialysis [31]. In Agarwal's study [12], a higher urea reduction ratio had a statistically significant protective effect from PH in a multivariate model. This may suggest a primary role for uraemic toxins in the pathogenesis of PH.

A major component of vascular dysfunction in kidney disease is due to vascular calcification. Therefore, calcification of the pulmonary vasculature has been proposed as a mechanism contributing to PH in CKD. One study correlated calcification score on scintigraphy scans with PH [32] and showed no association between the two. A number of studies have compared calcium, phosphate and parathyroid hormone (PTH) levels in patients with and without PH, but the majority have failed to demonstrate an association [3, 6, 15]. Only one study showed a positive correlation between echocardiographically estimated sPAP and calcium, phosphate and PTH in PD patients [13]. Failure to show a consistent relationship between bone parameters and PAP may be due to the complexity of the relationship between those parameters and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. For example, the association between phosphate and mortality is a J- or U-shaped relationship, presumably reflecting a high degree of inflammation and malnutrition in the low phosphate group and vascular dysfunction and calcification in the high phosphate group [33, 34]. Another factor adding to the difficulty in clarifying the relationship between bone parameters and PH is the fact that imaging techniques such as scintigraphy only detect large/medium vessel calcification, when small vessel pathology is more likely to be relevant if PH is caused by an arteriopathy.

The study by Agarwal [12] demonstrated that the use of vitamin D analogues has an adjusted odds ratio of 0.41 for the presence of PH. This is consistent with a body of evidence suggesting a protective effect of vitamin D against cardiovascular mortality in CKD [35]. However, interventional studies have yet to demonstrate a convincing cardiovascular benefit of active vitamin D administration in patients with kidney disease [36]. The recent EVOLVE study also failed to show a benefit of Cinacalcet treatment for hyperparathyroidism on a composite outcome of mortality and cardiovascular events in the primary analysis [37].

Thus far, no interventional studies have been performed in this group of patients. An understanding of the pathophysiology could help to identify therapeutic strategies. Identifying patients with a predominant vasculopathy could facilitate selection for treatment with vasodilator

therapies such as phosphodiesterase inhibitors, endothelin receptor antagonists or prostanoid analogues that have been shown to improve exercise tolerance and reduce pulmonary vascular resistance in non-uraemic PAH patients [38-40]. On the other hand, those with predominant cardiac components could benefit from strategies aimed at improving cardiac function such as the use of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system inhibitors, intense management of fluid status, or therapeutic reduction of AVF flow. It is of utmost importance that the latter group with LV pathology are differentiated from the PAH phenotype as the use of PAH treatments in patients with LV failure can result in pulmonary oedema or even death.

When designing interventional trials, it is worth bearing in mind that patients with advanced CKD may have dual pathology due to the high prevalence of systolic and diastolic cardiac dysfunction in this population. The presence of the latter should not automatically exclude the co-existence of a PAH-type process, and therefore, patients should be properly assessed for evidence of PAH and enrolled in clinical trials appropriately.

Conclusion: Identifying patients with potential reversibility of their PH could improve the selection process for kidney transplantation. Epidemiological data suggest that there is a high mortality rate among these patients which would preclude many of them from being considered for transplantation. Since there is some evidence that PH improves post-transplantation, patients with potential for reversibility might merit treatment with vasodilators prior to consideration for kidney transplantation.

Monitoring the pulmonary pressure would be warranted when symptoms worsen despite treatment. Right heart catheterization is a useful but inaccurate measurement of the PA pressure, and the contribution from the AV fistula can be determined with manual compression of the same while measuring PA pressure during RHC. An echocardiogram is a non-invasive simple means of measuring the RV systolic pressure. Blood flow in the fistula measured with a Doppler could be used to assess the need to reduce the flow by ligation or banding [23,30]. Pulmonary hypertension is an independent predictor of increased mortality in end-stage renal disease patients. It is vital to suspect and treat them at the earliest to prevent life-threatening complications. More research is needed in this area to understand the pathogenesis and therapeutic options further.

Until better understanding of the pathophysiology and effect of interventions such as the use of vasodilator treatments in this population becomes available, there is a call for a consensus involving nephrologists and PH specialists on how best to screen for, investigate and manage these patients, and a move away from simply labelling the condition as ‘heart failure’.

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